

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Sustainability report

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For more information on the project 4nse, link to <http://www.4nse.ch>

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Executive summary

The long-term success of a project should be measured using a detailed Sustainability Analysis of Technology (SAT), as described in the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and other sources. This approach guides the involved decision-makers and stakeholders to decide what actions to take in an attempt to deliver the best contribution to a sustainable development of the concerned society. Evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of the project's impacts, in terms of not only efficiency and costs, but also including environmental and social aspects, is essential for a broad acceptance by the population and government entities.

Important keywords in this context are: information, transparency and participatory decision-making, often neglected in the evaluation process of a project. The authors integrated the SAT method to assess the sustainability of the 4nse project, which consists of a self-developed, non-conventional and open-technology Environmental Monitoring System (EMS) network, tested in the three participating countries (Pakistan, Sri Lanka and Switzerland). The project intended to explore the most appropriate way to integrate the mentioned technologies into value added products, minimizing environmental and social difficulties due to limited capacity or improper natural resources management.

A detailed description of the current situation of the 4nse project and the definition of targets and their integration in the SAT methodology are revealed. To conclude, the results of an active stakeholder's participation in a SAT-based survey will be examined.

1 Introduction

Preventing natural risks such as droughts, floods and landslides, managing natural disasters mitigation and providing more detailed information for a better administration of water resources and crops irrigation, the usage of an EMS, turned out to be a reasonable approach. Furthermore, it could help improving the reliability of weather and climatological models and directly affect the economic, social and political spheres (Artiola, 2004). Unfortunately, in most developing and low-income countries, there is a lack of efficient EMS due to relatively high costs of hardware and software, often subject to proprietary code and rarely accessible to the public user. In fact, the policy of 'data hiding' is still a common fact in many governmental and private entities.

In contrast, the scope of the 4nse project (Acronym for: Four times Open Non-conventional System for Sensing the Environment), funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation, consists of the development of an open solution to monitor environmental parameters like rainfall, temperature, wind speed and direction. An EMS requires data management software usually hosted on a server structure. A self-developed data platform named istSOS, which is compliant with the Sensor Observation Service (SOS) standard of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and containing a server implemented interface to manage and dispatch observations from all kind of monitoring sensors, has been developed to receive, manage, validate and distribute acquired environmental data (Cannata, 2013). In this context, a solution to support also big data extending the istSOS capabilities has been included. In fact, a sensors network can hardly stress a data management system because of the several concurrent sensors and users and the long time series which every weather station can easily produce. Thus, a solution called istSOS-proxy has been developed (Strigaro D., 2018) as a single access point over multiple instances of istSOS databases, whose procedures are divided to balance the total load. The results on the effectiveness of the solution are promising, thanks to load testing simulations of different levels of concurrent users.

The project, after designing and testing the system, envisioned the installation of about 30 EMS in Sri Lanka and five in Pakistan and the set-up of a management and warning systems for floods and droughts. The system has been tested for almost two years to fully understand the real cost of ownership, data quality and applicability in real situations and derive scientific conclusions on the real applicability of these technologies. The global impact of the project is the empowering of developing countries in EMS development, management and evaluation.

Nevertheless, the success of a project should not be rated on its technical performance only; at least the same weight should be set on its future sustainability. This approach, called Sustainability Analysis of Technology (SAT) and described the United Nations Environment Programme UNEP, is an essential tool for involved decision-makers and stakeholders to decide what actions to take in an attempt to deliver the best contribution to a maintainable development of the society. The key features of SAT are in enumerated detail in a manual (United Nations Environment Programme, 2012) and include progressive assessment procedures through tiers, which allow addressing, screening and scoping; serving as entry points for decision-makers and finally optimizing information requirements.

Environmental, economical, technical and social aspects have to be taken into account involving governmental and non-governmental entities and, last but not least, the local

population (farmers, teachers, inhabitants, etc.). All this aids to produce a valuable Sustainability Analysis (SA), which should be objective, clear and transparent.

The SA has been largely addressed in literature and several definition has been reported. In general, the common principle is given by the objective of sustainability given by WCDE in the 1987 that states we should “meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”.

In a broad sense, SA can be defined as a process to support decision making in understanding the sustainability of a policy or an action:

- Sustainability assessment is a methodology “that can help decision-makers and policy-makers decide what actions they should take and should not take in an attempt to make society more sustainable” (Devuyst, 2001) or
- The goal of sustainability assessment is to pursue that “plans and activities make an optimal contribution to sustainable development” (Verheem, 2002).

When referring to a technology adoption, SA takes the specific objective of evaluating the advantages and disadvantages it may bring, not only in terms of costs and efficiency but also including environmental and social aspects. To produce assessments which are transparent and objective there’s the need to define a methodology/framework that clearly identifies the process leading to sustainability indicators and composite indexes which simplify, quantify, analyze and communicate complex information.

To this end, in UNEP manual this method has a clear focus on process and outcome and more attention to informed and participatory decision making. Within a SAT a proposed technology is addressed by evaluating the potential impacts on the environment, its effects on sustainable development and the expected cultural and socio-economic effects.

Within this work, the authors have adopted the SAT method to appraise the sustainability of the 4onse system, which is a non-conventional approach to hydro-meteorological monitoring based on open technology only: open software, hardware, standards and data. All these open technologies jointly contribute to create a system which is patent free and thus highly reproducible. Such a system has been developed and implemented in two case studies, one located in Sri Lanka along the Deduru Oya watershed and one located in Pakistan at the Institute of Space Technology in the Islamabad area.

In this complex context, a project-specific framework has been developed, which clearly identifies the sustainability indicators and composite indexes. In contrast to the pure technical abilities of the 4onse system, the SAT method was adopted to appraise the sustainability within decision-making processes and socio-economic effects of it. As explicitly stated in (United Nations Environment Programme, 2012), the project started directly with the operational level assessment and organized a stakeholder workshop to rate project specific criteria using the Environmental Technology Assessment (EnTA). The occupational activity of the participants was very extensive to obtain an EnTA including different points of view.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The SAT approach described above is the base of the analysis of the sustainability of the 4onse project. Following the SAT guidelines the first step consists of a situation analysis which includes:

- Baseline data collection
- Stakeholder consultation
- Mapping and analysis

These steps leads to identify and assess possible issues and their significance which must be solved by proper technology intervention or planning. Since the used technology has been chosen already during the project-planning period, Tier 1 (technology screening) and Tier 2 (scoping) were bounced and a detailed assessment (Tier 3) has been accomplished to present to the stakeholders for a comprehensive ranking as a result. In that sense the baseline data, defined in the UNEP manual as the initial collections of data which serve as a starting point for a project and also as a base for comparison, have been chosen and defined as the EnTA indicators.

Within the SAT’s operation level, four essential categories to address the sustainability have been considered as the UNEP manual suggests:

- Environmental considerations
- Social aspects
- Economical concerns
- Technical suitability

These categories have been taken and divided into specific indicators as requested by the SAT-methodology. At the beginning of the workshop, all participants have been divided into two teams considering the professional skills of their members (technical or social ambit):

1. Teachers [T]
2. Irrigation Department, Sri Lanka-Navy, Department of Agriculture, Rice Research & Development Institute [RNMI]

This selection was due to the number of participants, which were not equally distributed according to their profession. In a first survey, each member of a team could assign a note between one and five for each indicator of every category. Scores being assigned to indicators is a key element of the SAT methodology.

The first five winners of each category were selected and in a second round valuated again comparing three different kinds of EMS present in the territory of Sri Lanka:

- Pure manual EMS
- 4onse EMS
- Full automatic EMS

In all cases, it was possible that some scores remained blank since it was not mandatory to vote each single indicator. In the analysis, this fact has been taken into account normalizing the result of the scores to the total number of received scores.

2.1 Selected categories and indicators of the EnTA

The following EnTA categories (first row) and indicators have been defined at the beginning of the workshop:

Environmental	Social	Economical	Technical
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Water/Energy consumption	Job creation	Capital investment	Temp.resol. observation
Environmental emissions	Acceptance local culture	Operation/maintenance costs	Number of parameters
Noise/vibrations/emissions	Life quality	Payback period	Data quality/precision
Space/infrastructure requirements	Safety/health conditions	Availability financing	Communication
Carbon emissions	Improvement of local technical skills	Co-benefits	Data logging type
Visual impact	Local material accessibility	Costs of spare parts	Data logging time period
Lightning conductor		Cost of specialist intervention	Data transmission
Renewable energy		Material durability	Data recovery
Battery waste			Data archiving type
			Data accessibility

Table 1: Categories and indicators selected during the workshop

2.2 Indicator ranking

In a first step, the sum of the scores of an indicator (SSI) has been calculated. To get a normalized result of the score (NS), the SSI has been divided by the sum of scores of an entire category SSC:

$$NS = SSI / SSC$$

In this case, unscored elements (in case participants did not vote for a specific indicator) are not considered. NS multiplied per 100 gives the normalized result in percentage.

The results of the analysis are represented in histograms and radar charts to give a qualitative and quantitative impression of the participant’s opinion. The results for each category are discussed in the following chapters.

2.2.1 Environmental considerations

Both teams show a significant difference in assessing some of the defined criteria like the usage of renewable energy, important for teachers (social educated), but negligible for the RNMI team (more on the technical side). The same behaviour can be observed for carbon emission and noise/vibration indicators respectively. All other indicators seem to have a ‘common sense’ in the opinion of both teams. Remarkable is the low score for environmental emissions of both teams, regardless of the worldwide discussions and activities of climate change in these days.

Indicator ranking Teachers	Indicator ranking RNMI
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Figure 1: normalized percentage of consent for environmental indicators

2.2.2 Social aspects

An important role for both teams plays the job creation factor. On the other hand, the acceptance of local culture seems to have surprisingly low significance. A vast difference between both teams are obviously the safety/health conditions, high scored by RNMI and low by the teachers. Life quality seems equal important for the both groups while improvement of technical skills more for the teacher group.

Figure 2: normalized percentage of consent for social indicators

2.2.3 Economical concerns

It is not surprising that the capital investment turns out important for both teams. In addition, the material durability unifies the opinion of all team members with a low rating. The operation/maintenance costs divide the opinion of both teams, like the payback period, costs of spare parts and co-benefits.

Indicator ranking Teachers	Indicator ranking RNMI
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Figure 3: normalized percentage of consent for economical indicators

2.2.4 Technical suitability

The biggest difference between both teams can be seen in the technical category. As the only common sense turns out to be the importance of the data quality/precision indicator and the pettiness of the data logging type. One can imagine that communication plays an essential role for professionals in the social sector, while data recovery, data archiving type and the time resolution do not have a great importance. However, it is astonishing to see that data recovery, which is an essential point in Information Technology, has not been considered important by both teams.

Figure 4: normalized percentage of consent for technical indicators

The previously described results show a significant difference between both teams. Different aspects were considered in a different manner, which can be explained by the different professional or social background of the members. In figure 5 the indicators are represented by their priority for all categories:

Indicator priorities Teacher	Indicator priorities RNMI
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Figure 5: priority for all indicators of each category

The direct confrontation of the indicators between both teams can be seen in figure 6 for all categories. In the environmental section, Battery waste, Carbon emissions, Renewable energy and Space/infrastructure requirements represent the biggest differences (around five points) between both teams. However, Battery waste and Water/Energy consumption are the winners of the environmental concerns.

In the social category, the differences between the teams are more significant and reach up to 100% and more. While Improvement of local technical skills and Local material access show a huge divergence, while concerning the other indicators there seems to be more agreement. It is perhaps not surprising that Job creation is the major issue in this context.

A complete different picture represents the Economic and Technic categories. Hereby the disagreement of both teams is much more significant except for the Cost of specialist intervention (Economical) and the Data archiving type, Data quality, Data recovery and Number of parameters (Technical). In the economical point of view, the Capital investment is the leader of all concerns, while in the technical category the Data quality/precision is the leader for both teams, a unique situation.

Figure 6: confrontation between both teams for all indicators

2.3 EMS type ranking

As described in chapter 2, the five winning indicators of each category from the previous data evaluation were taken for the second voting, considering the three different EMS types present in Sri Lanka: manual, 4nse and full automatic. In fact, some manual EMS are still in use and need to be managed with a huge human effort (readout, i.e. person-hours and travel expenses). On the other hand, the Department of Meteorology of Sri Lanka uses full automatic high-precision weather stations, which are usually quite expensive and the maintenance is costly in time and money.

Summarizing the scores for the first five winning indicators of all categories and normalizing to the sum of all scores of a category, a ranking score was calculated for each category for each EMS type.

Figure 7: normalized score by category for teachers (left) and RNMI (right)

The result in ranking of all EMS types is illustrated in figure 8 for both teams. Hereby, the 4onse station has been identified from both teams as the best solution of all EMS types present in Sri Lanka using the chosen EnTA categories. In fact, this result seems the best compromise between the other two solutions, supported by the fact that an extensive comparison between the obtained data of the 4onse and a full automatic EMS located at the Institute of Earth Science in Lugano, Switzerland, has been accomplished (Strigaro D., 2018).

Figure 8: Total scores of the EMS type for both groups

3 Conclusions

The United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs UNDESA, stating “Technological change, particularly in developing countries, is not only about innovating at the frontier, but also about adapting existing products and processes to achieve higher levels of productivity as applicable to their local contexts. In this process, the ability of local firms and enterprises to access technological know-how is fundamental to shaping their ability to provide products and services, which we believe are essential to improve living standards, and that could also promote growth and competitiveness.” (Nayyer, 2012), is well aware that adapting existing technologies requires not only the wide acceptance of both: stakeholders and population but also their involvement in the development process. For that purpose, the SAT methodology has been developed to scientifically quantify this involvement. This methodology requires a ranking of technology options for the specific scenario using the highest scores for indicators of various categories given by participating stakeholders. These requirements have been fulfilled within this approach, using the defined indicators and categories and scoring them by participants with wide professional backgrounds of a workshop hold in Kurunegala in Sri Lanka. The result of the survey lead to a wide acceptance of the proposed open EMS,

designed and developed by the 4onse project without asking directly about the preferences between the candidate EMS types.

Reference

Artiola J.F., Pepper, I.L., Brusseau, M Environmental Monitoring and Characterization [Book]. - [s.l.] : Elsevier Academic Press, 2004.

Cannata M., Antonovic M., Molinari M., Pozzoni M. istSOS, a new sensor observation management system: software architecture and a real case for flood protection [Journal] // Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk. - 2013. - pp. 1-16.

Devuyst D., Introduction to sustainability assessment at the local level. In D Devuyst (Editor), How Green is the City? Sustainability assessment and the management of urban environments. Columbia University Press, New York, 2001

Nayyer D., United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) UN System Task Team on the Post-2015 UN Development Agenda. Population Dynamics: Thematic Think Piece. UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs, UN Population Fund [Journal]. - New York, NY, USA : [s.n.], 2012.

Strigaro D. Antonovic M., Cannata M., Cardoso M., Hoffmann M., Extending the scalability of istSOS within the 4onse project [Journal]. - 2018.

Strigaro D. Cannata M. Antonovic M. Boosting a Weather Monitoring System in Low Income Economies Using Open and Non-Conventional Systems: Data Quality Analysis [Journal]. - 2018.

United Nations Environment Programme Application of the sustainability assessment of technologies, methodology: Guidance Manual [Book]. - Osaka : [s.n.], 2012.

Verheem R, Tonk J. Strategic environmental assessment: one concept multiple forms. Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal 2000; 18:177-182.